

Barcelona Supercomputing Center

Annual Report 2021 Bioinfo4Women Programme

01 INTRODUCTION

This report summarises the main activities and achievements of the Bioinfo4Women (B4W) programme throughout 2021.

The B4W programme began in 2018 by organizing seminars delivered by women researchers and financially supporting three B4W fellows, women who start their careers as independent researchers outside the BSC. Since then, it has been growing and increasing its different activities, scope and impact annually.

The strategy and organization of the programme were shaped at the beginning of 2021. B4W organised a co-creation session with renowned researchers, such as Prof. Janet Thornton (EMBL-EBI), Dr Janet Kelso (MPI EVA) and Dr Isabelle Vernós (CRG), among others. During this session, participants identified the main problems and obstacles encountered by women researchers throughout their professional careers, as well as the elements or actions that allowed participants to overcome them and achieve professional success.

The strategy of the B4W programme was redefined after the analysis of the information collected in this co-creation session. It was organised around five strategic lines of action, and both ongoing and planned activities were redistributed around them.

Also in 2021 B4W formally defined its statutes, as well as a new working organisation of the programme, with the aim to improve its sustainability and its international connection, as well as a better distribution of efforts. For this, a series of working groups (WGs) have been established, each aligned to a line of action. These WGs were opened to participation to the whole Life Sciences Department at the BSC, and included members outside the core B4W team.

Each WG will define its specific annual objectives and carry out its activities autonomously, coordinated by the executive committee.

02 OBJECTIVES 2021

At the beginning of 2021 the B4W executive committee defined specific objectives for the annual plan, most of which were achieved by the end of the year, as well as additional unplanned actions, as summarised below.

Objective 1: Palau Macaya Series “Sex and Gender Bias in AI and Health”

In the period from March to June 2021, the B4W program organised the Palau Macaya conference series: "Sex and Gender Biases in Artificial Intelligence and Health" funded by a competitive call from "La Caixa" Foundation. The objectives of the conference series were:

- a. To provide a space for open debate between scientists and society about sex and gender biases in scientific research on health and artificial intelligence;
- b. To promote an international network of professional women in the area;
- c. To identify lines of action to address the problem and develop agreed strategies;

To achieve these objectives, B4W organised the following activities:

- Lectures delivered by renowned research experts in the area.
- Seminars with open debate between specialists and citizens, where the problem of sex and gender bias was addressed from two perspectives: personalised medicine and artificial intelligence.
- Workshops with specialists on the subject and different social groups.

The conference series was very well received and accumulated more than 2,000 views as of December 2021. All sessions were live streamed in English and Spanish and are available at the B4W programme website:

<https://bioinfo4women.bsc.es/sex-and-gender-bias-in-artificial-intelligence-and-health/>

The final report with the conclusions of the conference series was distributed to all contributors/participants and is publicly available.

Report - Sex and Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence and Health:
<https://zenodo.org/record/5513939>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5513939

At the request of the Parliament of Catalonia, the conclusions of the series were presented to the parliamentarians of the Equality and Feminism Commission (Gemma Lienas) and of the

Health Commission (Assumpta Escarp). Additionally, the European Parliament has requested the preparation of a report on the subject, expanding on the analysis of biases to different application areas of artificial intelligence (AI).

Objective 2: Formalise involvement within ISCB

The B4W programme worked for more than a year to achieve recognition by the ISCB as an affiliated group. Its statutes and its organisational structure were formally defined.

B4W statutes: <https://zenodo.org/record/5873532>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5873532.

B4W and ISCB held several meetings in which the objectives, organisation and activities were presented to explore how B4W could formally fit within the ISCB structure. As a result, in September 2021 ISCB created a new global category within its ISCB Affiliated Groups programme to accommodate B4W.

B4W at the ISCB Affiliated groups worldwide site: <https://www.iscb.org/iscb-affiliates-worldwide>

Objective 3: Gather ideas from the Life Sciences department about future activities

The initial idea for this objective was to develop a co-creation session with young research women from the Life Sciences department. It evolved into the activity “*Meeting with women leaders*”, open to all BSC employees, where informal, open discussions around challenges faced as women in research were held with women leaders in different fields, including research, business and politics. The report with the conclusions and ideas discussed is available at the B4W website.

Report - Summary and Conclusions Meeting with Women Leaders: <https://zenodo.org/record/5873599>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5873599

Objective 4: Expand international collaboration

A series of activities were developed to expand the international collaboration of the programme:

- Networking session within the Palau Macaya project with 15 institutions, including more than 20 women researchers and members of NGOs, international organisations and national public institutions, among other participants who work towards the promotion of women in scientific research. As a result, specific collaborations were established between some of the participating organizations, and a communication channel was created to share information and international funding/research calls.

- B4W slack channel link: https://join.slack.com/t/bioinfo4women-ngk2389/shared_invite/zt-11pfiwfbm-cxYm_Em6bB~xYT14BKoQtg
- An initial relationship has been established with national and international organisations to explore future collaborations and the development of activities, amongst which: BBMRI-ERIC, CNIO, ADITEC, ELIXIR, ISCB, Institut Pasteur, Roslin Institute and SIB.

Objective 5: Communicate success stories from B4W fellows

As the communication efforts were focussed on updating the corporate image and on the redesign of the B4W website, this activity was postponed to the following year.

Objective 6: Resume meetings with seminar speakers to introduce gender issues

During 2021, women researchers presenting at the B4W seminars were requested to share, at the end of the presentation of their scientific work, their experience as a woman in research, in terms of the development of their professional career, and including obstacles, motivations, solutions, positioning of their institution, etc.

Additionally, as part of the agenda for each speaker organised with researchers from the department after each seminar, a meeting with representatives of the B4W programme was scheduled to discuss the existing practices in their research centre to promote the career of women researchers, explain the B4W programme, and explore potential collaborations.

The recorded B4W seminars are available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cskLHA35h1w&list=PLbABsNMD2jhxBw0PZkeiM8b2cRSLgjOYs>.

03 OTHER ACTIVITIES

In addition to the activities aimed at achieving the annual objectives, the B4W programme has carried out the following activities during 2021:

- a) New image of the programme. A graphic design consultant designed a new logo and corporate image of the B4W programme to be applied on the website and social media.
- b) Bioinfo Women's Day (February 11). Like every year, B4W organised the department's open doors day. At this event, women researchers presented their work to master and under-graduate students. During these presentations, students are organised into small groups, promoting informal discussions where the researcher explained her work and establishing an open dialogue with students. This activity is organised within the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

This edition was held online with 9 BSC researchers and 43 participants.

c) B4W promoted joint discussions across all BSC departments to join forces towards achieving equality and diversity for the centre, a purely bottom-up effort. After brainstorming with employees from all departments and administration, it was decided to start by raising awareness on such inequalities, and this resulted in a joint presentation (BSC talks) for the whole centre, within the BSC day. The presentation is available at the BSC youtube channel: https://youtu.be/O4OONOfR_g4?t=3241.

d) ELIXIR Biohackathon. In November, B4W participated in the Biohackathon organized by ELIXIR with a competitively selected project. The project aimed at analysing and quantifying sex, gender, race and other biases in the ELIXIR biomedical repositories, and giving recommendations on the appropriate use of such data to avoid biases in AI algorithms.

As a result of the work done during the ELIXIR Biohackathon, two scientific articles are under preparation.

e) B4W outreach and participation in conferences. In 2021 B4W has participated in several conferences presenting the activities and/or the advances in the research line.

- Congreso internacional de Ciencia, Feminismo y Masculinidades - CICFEM 2021 (March, 2021). *“Bioinfo4women: Incorporando la perspectiva de sexo y género en Inteligencia Artificial en Salud” **selected talk** by researcher Dr Nataly Buslón.*
- EuroHPC Summit Week (March, 2021). *“ADVANCES IN COMPUTATIONAL BIOLOGY An Initiative That Promotes Women Researchers In The Computational Biology Field” by researcher Dr Nataly Buslón **as invited speaker.***
- STEM Women Day (April, 2021). *“Women in Data Science Barcelona 2021” by researcher Dr Nataly Buslón **as invited speaker.***
- OSSD Organization for the Study of Sex Differences (May, 2021). *“The Bioinfo4Women programme at the forefront of research in sex and gender differences in biomedicine and AI”. Nataly Buslón, Davide Cirillo, Àtia Cortés, Maria José Rementeria. **Selected as poster presentation.***
- BIOSpain (September, 2021). *“Bias in Artificial Intelligence” by María José Rementeria **as invited speaker.***
- VIII Bioinformatics Students Symposium, RSG-Spain (October, 2021). *“Perspectiva de sexo y género en la investigación” by researcher Dr Nataly Buslón **as invited speaker.***
- 2º Encuentro de Grupos de Igualdad de centros del CSIC (November, 2021).: *“Bioinfo4Women - Supporting women bioinformaticians and computational biologists” by María José Rementeria **selected a poster presentation.***

- PRISMA Conference “Resilient voices for difficult times” (November, 2021). Dr Davide Cirillo and Dr Nataly Buslón **as invited speakers**.
 - Conversatorio Sesgos raciales y de género en inteligencia artificial, Semana de la Ingeniería (November, 2021). researcher Dr Nataly Buslón **as invited Speaker**.
- f) Finally, the B4W programme defined and delivered a course on "Sex and gender biases in science" included in the BSC PhD Training Programme (November, 2021), mandatory for all first-year PhD students at the BSC, by researchers: Dr Davide Cirillo, Dr Atia Cortés and Dr Nataly Buslón.